

REVITALIZING INDIAN MANUFACTURING: MAKE IN INDIA'S ROLE IN EMPOWERING MSMEs

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ABSTRACT

India's economy, which ranks sixth in the world in terms of nominal GDP, is among the fastest growing in the world. With the goal of transforming India into a global manufacturing hub Narendra Modi ji, the PM of India, announced the Make in India initiative on September 25, 2014, as an international marketing approach to attract investments from businesses all over the globe and make India the manufacturing hub. India has started a comprehensive "Make in India" movement in an attempt to become a worldwide manufacturing powerhouse. Numerous reforms were implemented to support India's manufacturing, design, MSMEs, innovation, and startups. As part of its claimed objective of making India economically self-reliant, the "Atma Nirbhar Bharat" programme, which was launched in 2020, was also designed to further stimulate local manufacturing. The "Make in India" programme, which aims to attract investments and collaborations between Indian and international businesses in the manufacturing sector, is said to be extremely pertinent for India's MSMEs. The MSME sector is the nursery of industrialization of the country. This present study relies on secondary data. This article examines the concept of Make in India initiative's contribution to the growth of the manufacturing sector. This paper also aims to comprehend the advantages of the Make in India campaign for MSMEs and the government's support in fostering this industry's expansion and lastly gives some suggestions for successful implementation of this campaign.

Keywords: Make in India; MSMEs; GDP; Economy; Manufacturing Sector; Investment

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INTRODUCTION

The "Make in India" initiative, introduced in September 2014, is a flagship program aimed at transforming India into a global manufacturing hub. By promoting domestic manufacturing, the initiative aspires to reduce dependence on imports, generate employment, and address India's persistent negative balance of payments. It sets an ambitious target of increasing the manufacturing sector's contribution to GDP to 25% by 2025, signaling a commitment to achieving self-reliance and economic sustainability (GOI, 2014; Mukherjee & Gupta, 2018). As one of the first "Vocal for Local" campaigns, this program has garnered international recognition for showcasing India's industrial potential while fostering local innovation and entrepreneurship (Bhattacharya, 2020).

The initiative became even more critical following the economic disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic led to significant challenges, including supply chain disruptions, job losses, and a contraction in GDP growth (Das & Kumar, 2022). Relaunching "Make in India" is essential to accelerate recovery, reduce import dependence, and build a resilient manufacturing base. With a renewed focus, the campaign seeks to strengthen India's position as a global manufacturing leader by fostering innovation, attracting foreign direct investment (FDI), and encouraging the development of advanced infrastructure (Kumar & Singh, 2021). These steps align with the broader objective of creating a globally competitive manufacturing ecosystem capable of driving economic growth and self-reliance (Srinivasan et al., 2022).

A central question arises: *How can the "Make in India" initiative transform India's manufacturing sector to drive self-reliance, economic growth, and global competitiveness?*

To address this, the study examines specific dimensions of the initiative. First, it explores the core concept and vision of "Make in India" to understand its foundational goals. Second, it evaluates the initiative's contributions to India's manufacturing sector, focusing on GDP growth, employment generation, and export potential. Third, it examines key measures undertaken by the Government of India (GOI) to support Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), which constitute a critical component of India's industrial base. Finally, it proposes recommendations for enhancing the initiative's effectiveness and achieving its intended outcomes.

The study addresses the following research questions:

- RQ1: What is the concept and vision of the "Make in India" campaign?
- RQ2: How has the "Make in India" initiative contributed to the growth of the manufacturing sector in India?
- RQ3: What key measures has the Government of India implemented to support MSMEs and the manufacturing sector under the "Make in India" program?
- RQ4: What suggestions can be made to ensure the successful implementation of the "Make in India" campaign?

The "Make in India" initiative has undergone significant evolution since its inception. Under "Make in India 2.0," the program now targets 27 critical sectors, including 24 identified sub-sectors such as electronics, textiles, auto components, drones, and medical devices (GOI, 2023; NITI Aayog, 2023). These efforts aim to enhance domestic manufacturing, boost employment opportunities, and increase export capacity.

The Ministry of Commerce has adopted coordinated strategies to promote these sub-sectors by leveraging policy reforms, technological advancements, and public-private partnerships (Chopra, 2022). Reports suggest that this sectoral focus is essential for integrating India into global supply chains and ensuring economic resilience in a post-pandemic world (Rajan & Sinha, 2023).

The campaign's success is anchored on four pillars: New Processes, New Infrastructure, New Sectors, and New Mindset. These pillars represent a comprehensive strategy to foster entrepreneurship, improve manufacturing efficiency, and enhance innovation across industries (Ministry of Commerce, 2024). By enabling structural reforms, developing high-quality infrastructure, and focusing on sector-specific interventions, "Make in India" aims to overcome existing barriers and position India as a leading global manufacturing hub (Prakash et al., 2021). This holistic framework ensures that the government's policies align with industrial needs, paving the way for sustainable growth and economic self-reliance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The "Make in India" initiative, launched by Prime Minister Narendra Modi on September 25, 2014, aims to transform India into a global manufacturing hub by attracting foreign investments and boosting the manufacturing sector. The campaign focuses on 25 key sectors, including manufacturing, and highlights the critical role of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in driving economic growth and job creation (Bagaria, 2018). The initiative's objective is to increase the manufacturing sector's contribution to India's GDP from 16% to 25% by 2022 and create 100 million jobs (Aggarwal, 2018). To achieve these goals, the campaign emphasizes improving the ease of doing business, enhancing infrastructure, and promoting skill development.

MSMEs, which are vital to the Indian economy, play a crucial role in the success of "Make in India." They contribute significantly to employment, exports, and GDP growth (Kumar & Seema, 2018). According to Shettar and Sheshgiri (2017), MSMEs account for about 45% of the manufacturing output and 40% of exports in India, providing employment to over 120 million people. Recognizing the importance of MSMEs, the "Make in India" campaign aims to provide them with the necessary support, including policy reforms, financial incentives, and initiatives to foster innovation and technology adoption.

The campaign has had a positive impact on MSMEs by creating a more conducive environment for growth and development. Increased foreign direct investment (FDI) in the manufacturing sector has provided MSMEs access to advanced technology, capital, and new markets (Gaur, 2015). Additionally, the implementation of the Goods and Services Tax (GST) has simplified the tax structure, reducing compliance costs for MSMEs and improving their competitiveness (Aggarwal, 2018). The introduction of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (IBC) has strengthened the business environment by offering a robust framework for resolving insolvencies, which enhances entrepreneurial confidence and reduces financial risks.

However, despite these positive developments, MSMEs face several challenges that hinder their full potential. Access to finance remains a significant issue, with many MSMEs struggling to secure the necessary credit for expansion and innovation (Kumar & Seema, 2018). Infrastructure bottlenecks, regulatory hurdles, and a lack of skilled labor and technological advancements further exacerbate the difficulties faced by MSMEs in competing with larger enterprises.

Additionally, MSMEs often have limited access to international markets, which restricts their ability to scale and grow. Overcoming these challenges is crucial for the success of the "Make in India" campaign and the broader growth of the manufacturing sector.

Several studies highlight the importance of improving access to finance for MSMEs. Bagaria (2018) emphasizes the need for banking reforms to enhance credit availability and suggests promoting alternative financing mechanisms such as venture capital and crowdfunding. Gaur (2015) underlines the importance of investing in infrastructure development to reduce logistical costs and improve MSMEs' competitiveness in the global market.

In addition to these financial and infrastructural improvements, there is a growing recognition of the need for skill development initiatives to enhance the productivity of the MSME workforce. Shettar and Sheshgiri (2017) argue that targeted training programs, in collaboration with educational institutions, are essential to equip MSME employees with the skills needed to adapt to technological advancements and the demands of a rapidly changing industrial landscape. Skill development is crucial for improving productivity, driving innovation, and ensuring MSMEs remain competitive in the global market.

The "Make in India" campaign also promotes investment in new and emerging sectors to stimulate industrial growth. According to Soundhariya (2015), the campaign effectively positions India as both an investment destination and a global manufacturing powerhouse. This is evident in the diverse sectors targeted by the initiative, which range from traditional industries like automobiles to emerging fields such as biotechnology and defense. By focusing on these high-potential sectors, "Make in India" aims to create a more diverse and resilient manufacturing ecosystem.

The government's efforts to simplify regulations, ease export procedures, and establish an Investor Facilitation Cell have been crucial in promoting India as a manufacturing hub. Bhatia and Agrawal (2018) highlight the success of small initiatives, such as easing export regulations, which have served as significant accelerators for the campaign. These steps have helped build a favorable business environment, encouraging both domestic and foreign investments in the manufacturing sector.

Despite these positive strides, MSMEs continue to face challenges in accessing international markets and achieving economies of scale. Addressing these challenges is critical for ensuring the long-term success of the "Make in India" initiative. According to Sahoo (2018), steps taken by the government, such as opening new sectors to foreign direct investment (FDI) and simplifying FDI policy restrictions, have helped to attract foreign capital and technology, which can further enhance the growth potential of MSMEs.

The "Make in India" campaign's success depends not only on enhancing financial access and infrastructure but also on a broader effort to address the skills gap. The importance of skill development is underscored by Shettar (2017), who emphasizes that targeted training programs and collaborations with educational institutions are essential to improving the MSME workforce's productivity. These initiatives can provide workers with the necessary skills to adapt to technological changes, foster innovation, and meet the evolving demands of global markets.

The "Make in India" initiative has made significant strides in transforming India into a global manufacturing hub. By focusing on key sectors and supporting MSMEs, the campaign has contributed to the growth of India's manufacturing sector, increased foreign investments, and created a more favorable business environment. However, challenges such as access to finance, infrastructure gaps, regulatory issues, and the need for skill development remain significant barriers. Addressing these challenges through targeted policy reforms, infrastructure investments, and skill development programs will be essential to ensuring the continued success of the "Make in India" initiative and achieving its goals of self-reliance, economic growth, and global competitiveness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research began with gathering background information on the manufacturing sector, including its history, current status, market size, and major investments. The role of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and relevant government initiatives were also explored. Given the time constraints, data for the study was primarily collected from secondary sources.

Key sources of secondary data included official documents such as the annual reports of MSMEs, the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion's database, and the Reserve Bank of India's Database on the Indian Economy. Additionally, information was sourced from a variety of research papers, journals, newspapers, articles, and official publications like Press Information Bureau (PIB) reports. These sources provided valuable insights into the manufacturing sector's development, challenges, and opportunities, particularly concerning MSMEs.

The research adopted an exploratory research design to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. This approach enabled the researcher to delve deeper into the complexities of the manufacturing sector and MSMEs, including government policies, economic implications, and industry dynamics. The exploratory design also facilitated the identification of key trends, issues, and gaps in the current literature and available data.

By leveraging a range of secondary sources, the study aimed to capture diverse perspectives and gain a holistic view of the research objectives. This methodology allowed for a broad exploration of the manufacturing sector and the role of MSMEs in the context of India's economic growth and the "Make in India" initiative.

The use of secondary data and exploratory research design proved effective in gathering in-depth information within the limited timeframe. The methodology also ensured that the research was grounded in reliable and credible sources, providing a solid foundation for analysis and conclusions.

OVERVIEW OF INDIA'S MANUFACTURING SECTOR

Manufacturing is considered a crucial driver of future growth, providing a foundation for long-term economic progress. For India, revitalizing the manufacturing sector is seen as a vital step towards achieving sustainable economic development. Historically, the manufacturing sector has been an Achilles' heel for India's economy, and any country seeking a stable and robust economy must build a strong manufacturing base (India Brand Equity Foundation, 2021).

The government's "Make in India" initiative has significantly accelerated the sector's development, focusing on areas such as electronics, healthcare, and infrastructure, with positive results already visible. By building industrial corridors and smart cities, India is positioning itself as a global manufacturing hub, equipped with cutting-edge technology, high-speed connectivity, and integrated logistics (Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade [DPIIT], 2020). The objective of "Make in India" is to foster both domestic and international investments, making India a competitive player in the global manufacturing sector (DPIIT, 2020).

The Production-Linked Incentive (PLI) Scheme, introduced with an investment of Rs. 1.97 lakh crore over five years, aims to further boost manufacturing across 13 sectors (DPIIT, 2020). This initiative is set to propel India's manufacturing capability, contributing to long-term economic growth. Skill development across both rural and urban areas is essential to the success of this program, helping create jobs and increase global competitiveness (Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship, 2021).

India's transformation from an agricultural-based economy to a modern, industrialized economy heavily relies on expanding its manufacturing sector. The sector has the potential to generate jobs for India's young labor force, offering opportunities for inclusive growth and economic empowerment (World Bank, 2020).

Market Size of the Manufacturing Sector

India's Manufacturing Purchasing Managers' Index (PMI) increased from 54 in March 2022 to 54.7 in April 2022, indicating positive growth within the sector (IHS Markit, 2022). This growth is primarily driven by key sectors such as capital goods, the automobile industry, and consumer goods, which have shown robust performance and increased output. The rise in PMI suggests an expansion in manufacturing activity, reflecting improved demand and production efficiency.

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has also seen a significant rise following the introduction of the "Make in India" initiative. FDI inflows into the manufacturing sector increased from US\$ 3.98 billion in the fiscal year 2019-20 to US\$ 6.86 billion in the fiscal year 2020-21 (Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade [DPIIT], 2020). This surge in FDI is attributed to policy reforms, ease of doing business, and various incentives offered under the "Make in India" campaign, which have made India an attractive destination for global investors.

India's GDP for the fiscal year (FY) 2021–22 was estimated at Rs. 51.23 lakh crore (US\$ 694.93 billion), with the manufacturing Gross Value Added (GVA) for the third quarter of FY 2021–22 recorded at US\$ 77.47 billion (Ministry of Finance, 2021). The manufacturing sector has shown a remarkable rebound post-COVID-19, with capacity utilization increasing to 72% in the second quarter of FY 2021–22 (Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry [FICCI], 2021). This recovery is indicative of the sector's resilience and the effectiveness of government support measures.

The manufacturing GDP in India grew from 5922.68 INR billion in the fourth quarter of 2021 to 6764.14 INR billion in the first quarter of 2022 (Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation [MoSPI], 2021). This growth demonstrates a substantial recovery and a positive outlook for India's manufacturing sector, driven by increased domestic and international demand, improved industrial production, and policy support.

Figure 1: Capacity Utilization in Manufacturing Sector

SOURCE: <https://www.ibef.org/industry/manufacturing-sector-india>

Major Investment

From April 2000 to March 2022, India received significant foreign investments aimed at bolstering its manufacturing capabilities. In FY 2021–2022, India attracted US\$ 58.77 billion in FDI (DPIIT, 2022). This increase in foreign investment underscores the global confidence in India's manufacturing potential and the impact of the "Make in India" campaign.

One major development was the approval of a Production Linked Incentive (PLI) scheme worth Rs. 26,058 crore (US\$ 3.53 billion) for the drone and automotive industries (DPIIT, 2021). The PLI scheme aims to boost manufacturing output, promote advanced technologies, and make India a hub for innovation in these sectors. The scheme offers financial incentives to manufacturers based on their incremental sales, thereby encouraging higher production and investment.

The chemical and pharmaceutical sectors have also witnessed increased foreign investments. The FDI inflows in these sectors were US\$ 19.45 billion and US\$ 19.41 billion, respectively, reflecting strong investor interest and the potential for growth (DPIIT, 2021). These investments are expected to enhance the manufacturing capabilities of India, especially in producing high-quality chemicals and pharmaceuticals for domestic and international markets.

Additionally, international partnerships have reinforced India's manufacturing capacities, particularly in electronics. Wistron Corp.'s collaboration with Optiemus Electronics to manufacture smartphones and laptops is a notable example (Optiemus Electronics, 2021). This partnership aims to leverage India's skilled workforce and cost advantages to produce high-quality electronic products for global markets.

The "Make in India" campaign has attracted high-profile investors like Elon Musk, who announced plans for Tesla to establish a manufacturing presence in India (Tesla, 2021). This move is expected to boost the electric vehicle (EV) sector and promote sustainable manufacturing practices in the country. Similarly, Samsung's decision to relocate its mobile and IT display manufacturing unit from China to Uttar Pradesh marks a significant development in India's manufacturing landscape. Samsung's investment of Rs. 4,825 crore (US\$ 650.42 million) will create job opportunities and enhance India's position as a global electronics manufacturing hub (DPIIT, 2021).

Figure 2: Major Investments Since 2019

Source: Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (MOSPI)

Role of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) for “Make in India”

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a pivotal role in India’s economic growth, particularly within the manufacturing sector. MSMEs constitute a significant portion of Indian manufacturing and benefit from the “Make in India” campaign (Ministry of MSME, 2021). These enterprises are essential to India's inclusive economic growth, providing employment opportunities to over 130 million people and contributing 62% of total exports (Ministry of MSME, 2021).

The government has introduced several programs to support MSMEs, including financing, technology, infrastructure, and skill development initiatives. These efforts help address regional imbalances and promote equitable wealth distribution across the country. MSMEs contribute significantly to the development of India’s manufacturing capabilities and are integral to the success of the “Make in India” vision (DPIIT, 2021).

The “Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan” (Self-Reliant India Campaign) launched in May 2020 further emphasized the importance of MSMEs in promoting self-sufficiency and reducing reliance on imports (Ministry of MSME, 2020). The growth of local entrepreneurship in MSMEs has contributed to India’s rising stature as a manufacturing powerhouse, with the sector playing a key role in achieving the government’s target of a \$5 trillion economy by 2025 (DPIIT, 2020).

MSMEs' Contribution to GDP

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are a significant contributor to India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). According to the Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation (MoSPI) (2021), the manufacturing sector of MSMEs accounts for 7.09% of the GDP, while the services sector contributes 30.5% of the GDP. This highlights the vital role MSMEs play in the economic structure of India, providing a diversified economic base and fostering growth in various sectors.

The contribution of MSME manufacturing to total manufacturing Gross Value Added (GVA) has remained steady at 36.9% over the past two years (MoSPI, 2021). This consistent contribution underscores the resilience and stability of MSMEs within the manufacturing sector, even amidst economic fluctuations. MSMEs' significant share in GVA indicates their crucial role in the industrial output and economic stability of the country.

Furthermore, MSMEs account for approximately 50% of India's exports, reinforcing their role as crucial drivers of economic growth (Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics, 2021). This substantial share in exports not only showcases the global competitiveness of Indian MSMEs but also highlights their importance in earning foreign exchange and enhancing the country's trade balance. The ability of MSMEs to cater to international markets reflects their adaptability and innovation in meeting global standards.

In addition to their contributions to GDP and exports, MSMEs are also major employers in India, providing employment to over 120 million people (Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises, 2021). This employment generation is critical in a country like India, where there is a need for widespread job creation to support the growing population. MSMEs help in creating inclusive growth by offering job opportunities across various regions, thereby reducing regional disparities.

Moreover, MSMEs contribute significantly to the socio-economic development of the country by fostering entrepreneurship and innovation. They provide a platform for new and emerging entrepreneurs, allowing them to bring new ideas to the market and enhance the overall innovation ecosystem of the country (Kadian, 2015). This entrepreneurial spirit helps in driving economic dynamism and diversity, which are essential for sustained economic development.

Despite their significant contributions, MSMEs face numerous challenges that hinder their growth potential. Access to finance remains one of the primary hurdles, as many MSMEs struggle to secure adequate funding from traditional financial institutions. The government has been implementing various schemes and initiatives to enhance credit availability for MSMEs, but gaps still exist that need to be addressed (Sahoo, 2018).

Additionally, infrastructural bottlenecks, regulatory complexities, and lack of skilled labor continue to pose challenges for MSMEs. Addressing these issues through comprehensive policy measures and support mechanisms is crucial for leveraging the full potential of MSMEs in driving economic growth.

Government Initiatives for Manufacturing Sector and MSMEs

The Indian government has launched several initiatives to boost the manufacturing sector and support MSMEs, recognizing their pivotal role in economic growth and employment generation.

One of the notable initiatives is the Electronics and IT Hardware Manufacturing Promotion Scheme, which has allocated Rs. 2,403 crore (US\$ 315 million) to enhance the electronics manufacturing sector in India (Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade [DPIIT], 2021). This scheme aims to make India a global leader in electronics and IT hardware manufacturing by providing financial incentives to domestic manufacturers.

Additionally, the government introduced the Production Linked Incentive (PLI) scheme for semiconductor manufacturing, worth Rs. 760 billion (US\$ 9.71 billion), to position India as a key player in the global semiconductor market (Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology [MeitY], 2021). The PLI scheme is designed to attract large investments in semiconductor fabrication units, assembly, testing, and packaging, thereby creating a robust semiconductor ecosystem in India.

In July 2021, the government launched six technological innovation platforms to foster innovation and drive advancements in manufacturing (MeitY, 2021). These platforms are intended to facilitate collaboration among industry, academia, and research institutions, promoting the development of cutting-edge technologies and enhancing the competitiveness of Indian manufacturing.

Project-75 is another significant initiative, which involves the construction of six conventional submarines for Rs. 50,000 crore (US\$ 6.7 billion), underscoring the government's commitment to strengthening India's defense manufacturing capabilities (Ministry of Defence, 2021). This project is expected to boost the indigenous defense manufacturing sector and reduce dependency on foreign suppliers.

To support MSMEs, the government has implemented programs like the Prime Minister's Employment Generation Program (PMEGP) and Raising and Accelerating MSME Performance (RAMP), with a combined budget of INR 6,000 crore (Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises [MSME], 2021). PMEGP aims to generate sustainable employment opportunities in rural and urban areas by setting up new self-employment ventures and micro-enterprises. RAMP focuses on enhancing the competitiveness and productivity of MSMEs through financial assistance, technology upgradation, and capacity building initiatives.

Furthermore, the government has introduced various schemes to improve access to finance for MSMEs. The Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Micro and Small Enterprises (CGTMSE) provides credit guarantees to banks and financial institutions for loans extended to MSMEs, mitigating the risk associated with lending to small businesses (MSME, 2021). Additionally, the MUDRA (Micro Units Development and Refinance Agency) scheme offers refinancing support to micro-enterprises, promoting financial inclusion and entrepreneurship.

The government has also emphasized skill development and training programs to address the skill gap in the MSME sector. Initiatives like the Skill India Mission and the Entrepreneurship Development Program aim to equip the workforce with relevant skills and knowledge, enhancing their employability and productivity (DPIIT, 2021).

Moreover, the Digital MSME Scheme promotes the adoption of digital tools and technologies among MSMEs to improve their operational efficiency and market reach. This scheme provides financial assistance for implementing cloud computing solutions and other digital technologies, enabling MSMEs to leverage digital platforms for business growth (MeitY, 2021).

CHALLENGES AND ADVANTAGES OF MSMEs

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) face several challenges that hinder their growth and development, despite their critical role in the economy. One of the most significant challenges is access to finance. Many MSMEs struggle to secure financing due to limited credit history, high-interest rates, and stringent lending criteria set by financial institutions (Srinivasan, 2019). This restricts their ability to invest in new technologies, expand operations, or even maintain liquidity during financial crises. While the government has introduced schemes like the Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Micro and Small Enterprises (CGTMSE), their implementation and reach have been limited (DPIIT, 2021).

Another major challenge is the lack of technological advancements. Many MSMEs cannot afford to invest in the latest technologies due to high initial costs, lack of skilled labor, and limited access to technical expertise (Natarajan, 2020). As industries increasingly adopt automation, artificial intelligence, and data analytics, MSMEs risk falling behind if they fail to innovate and modernize their operations.

Regulatory and compliance challenges are also a major issue. MSMEs often face complex and frequently changing regulations, such as tax laws, labor laws, and other compliance requirements, which add to their operational burden (Goyal, 2018). The introduction of Goods and Services Tax (GST) and other regulatory changes have sometimes been difficult for MSMEs to navigate, especially due to their limited resources and lack of expert guidance (Ministry of Finance, 2021).

Furthermore, infrastructure limitations such as inadequate roads, unreliable electricity, and poor internet connectivity in rural and semi-urban areas hinder MSMEs' ability to operate efficiently and expand (Kumar & Gupta, 2019). The lack of quality infrastructure increases operational costs and reduces competitiveness.

Skilled labor shortages present another challenge for MSMEs. Although India has a large labor force, many MSMEs struggle to find workers with the necessary technical and managerial skills to drive their businesses forward. This skill gap limits their ability to innovate and scale (Banerjee & Duflo, 2019).

Finally, limited market access remains a significant issue for MSMEs. Due to their smaller scale, these enterprises often lack the resources to engage in large-scale marketing or tap into international markets. Despite government initiatives aimed at promoting exports, MSMEs still face barriers such as complex export regulations and poor logistical support (Directorate General of Commercial Intelligence and Statistics, 2021).

Advantages of MSMEs

Despite the challenges, MSMEs offer numerous advantages that contribute significantly to economic development. One of the key benefits is their role in employment generation. MSMEs are responsible for providing employment to millions of people, especially in rural and semi-urban areas. In fact, MSMEs employ over 130 million people, making them the second-largest employers after agriculture (Ministry of MSME, 2021). By offering flexible job opportunities, MSMEs help reduce unemployment and underemployment.

Another important advantage is their contribution to GDP and exports. MSMEs account for approximately 30% of India's GDP and nearly 50% of total exports (Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation [MoSPI], 2021). They are especially significant in sectors such as textiles, chemicals, food processing, and electronics. MSMEs drive export-led growth and help diversify the country's economic base, reducing dependence on large industries (Aggarwal, 2018).

MSMEs are also more flexible and innovative than larger enterprises. Their small size allows them to quickly adapt to changing market demands and customer preferences (Kumar & Seema, 2018). This flexibility enables them to capitalize on niche markets and develop unique products. Many MSMEs are at the forefront of innovation, developing new technologies or offering services that cater to specific customer needs (Sahoo, 2018).

The promotion of regional development is another advantage of MSMEs. By establishing businesses in rural and remote areas, MSMEs help reduce regional economic disparities. They contribute to the development of infrastructure, services, and skills in less developed regions, leading to a more balanced distribution of wealth and opportunities. This decentralization of economic activity also helps alleviate migration pressures on urban areas (Shettar & Sheshgiri, 2017).

MSMEs also play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurship. They provide opportunities for individuals to start their own businesses with relatively low capital investment (Kadian, 2015). With government support, such as the "Startup India" initiative, MSMEs are becoming the foundation for new entrepreneurial ventures, helping to fuel India's growing startup ecosystem.

Finally, the government support and schemes aimed at MSMEs are substantial. The Indian government has launched several initiatives like the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY), Atmanirbhar Bharat, and the Digital MSME Scheme, providing financial assistance, technological support, and market access. These schemes help MSMEs overcome some of the barriers they face, enhancing their growth potential (DPIIT, 2021).

THE ROAD AHEAD

To ensure the sustained growth and success of the "Make in India" initiative, the government must focus on several strategic areas, fostering an environment conducive to innovation, infrastructure development, and economic growth.

Governments should prioritize establishing knowledge clusters to foster the evolution of innovative capabilities. According to Banerjee and Duflo (2019), India requires a confluence of financial resources, talent, entrepreneurial zeal, and knowledge to nurture an environment where innovation thrives. These clusters can serve as hubs for research and development (R&D), providing MSMEs with access to advanced technologies and expertise.

In today's mechanized world, it is challenging to prosper without integrating infrastructure and technology. To sustain the growing manufacturing sector, flexible tax policies need to be implemented to encourage the import of technology and support investments in this vital area (Kumar & Gupta, 2019). Such policies can make advanced machinery and equipment more affordable for MSMEs, facilitating their modernization and competitiveness.

The government must dedicate more efforts toward creating the necessary infrastructure to ensure the effective and successful execution of the Make in India plan across the country. This initiative relies heavily on developing robust infrastructure to facilitate manufacturing and industrial growth (Goyal, 2018). Improved infrastructure, including better transportation networks, reliable power supply, and enhanced digital connectivity, is critical for reducing operational costs and improving efficiency.

As part of the Make in India initiative, the government should provide targeted policy measures to promote and support MSMEs directly or indirectly linked to India's agricultural industry. These MSMEs play a crucial role in enhancing the nation's agricultural economy and should be given due encouragement and support (Kadian, 2015). Agro-based MSMEs, in particular, have significant growth potential and require additional backing to unlock their capabilities.

Further incentives and assistance must be provided to agro-based MSMEs and agro-based manufacturing ventures under the Make in India initiative. According to Soundharya (2015), these sectors hold significant potential for growth and need additional backing to unlock their full capabilities. Providing financial incentives, technical support, and market access can help these MSMEs expand and innovate.

While pursuing the objective of making India a global manufacturing center, the ecological balance must not be overlooked. Environmental protection is integral to the nation's sustainable growth and should be prioritized alongside industrial development (Shettar & Sheshgiri, 2017). Implementing sustainable practices and adhering to environmental regulations can ensure that economic growth does not come at the expense of the environment.

The success of Make in India also depends on a substantial increase in the number of skill development institutions to harness the potential of India's unskilled youth. The government must focus on the root causes of unemployment and provide solutions that help the youth, who are currently underemployed, find meaningful work (Ministry of MSME, 2021). Skill development programs and vocational training can equip the workforce with the necessary skills to meet industry demands.

To truly scale MSMEs, there needs to be a significant increase in financial and human resources. This will ensure that more businesses can qualify as MSMEs and that current MSMEs can improve their capital base, aligning with global standards (Sahoo, 2018). Access to affordable credit, investment in human capital, and capacity-building initiatives are essential for scaling MSMEs.

Labour laws should be amended with a balanced approach, ensuring that the interests of workers are not disregarded while also fostering an increase in employment opportunities. Simplifying exit regulations for Indian and foreign firms would also reduce the burden of unnecessary regulations, enabling businesses to thrive (Goyal, 2018). A balanced regulatory framework can attract investments and promote a business-friendly environment.

Increasing corporate research and development (R&D) within the country is essential to enhancing national businesses' competitiveness on the global stage. A stronger focus on R&D would contribute to innovation and drive the growth of Indian industries (Banerjee & Duflo, 2019). Government incentives and partnerships with academic institutions can boost R&D activities.

MSMEs must be granted easier access to financing, which would prevent many promising ventures from stalling or being delayed due to a lack of funds. Simplified financing options would help businesses scale and sustain their operations (Srinivasan, 2019). Initiatives like the Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Micro and Small Enterprises (CGTMSE) can be expanded to provide broader coverage and easier access.

Liquidity is a critical concern for MSMEs, as firms require working capital to operate. Banks should consider lending MSMEs up to 35% of a business's turnover as working capital, which would significantly benefit the sector (Ministry of Finance, 2021). Adequate working capital can ensure smooth operations and help businesses manage cash flow challenges.

India's manufacturing sector cannot expand successfully by focusing solely on the domestic market. To drive economic growth, the government should encourage more foreign direct investment (FDI) that is export-focused. This would directly impact export growth and subsequently boost economic growth (DPIIT, 2021). Encouraging export-oriented FDI can integrate India into global value chains and enhance its export performance.

If the government implements even a fraction of these recommendations, MSME units will undoubtedly become self-reliant (atma nirbhar), offering a substantial boost to the Indian economy and potentially surpassing nations like China in international marketplaces (Soundharya, 2015).

CONCLUSION

From the extensive material reviewed, it has been concluded that the "Make in India" campaign serves as an outstanding opportunity for all Indian economic elements, supplying the Indian economy and related sectors with significant advantages. This initiative is setting a new standard for the Indian economy and GDP, enabling it to compete with and surpass some of the world's greatest economies, such as China, France, and Germany, which have traditionally questioned India's economic potential. By 2030, India is poised to contribute more than US\$ 500 billion annually to the global economy and become a global manufacturing powerhouse.

The Government of India continues to place a high priority on fostering a favorable environment for the expansion of the manufacturing sector. The manufacturing industry in India has the potential to become one of the fastest-growing sectors, generating enormous amounts of work, which will allow a sizable portion of the population to progress toward gainful employment. The GOI has made 'Make in India' a fundamental policy program to stimulate and accelerate the country's manufacturing sector growth, showcasing the government's commitment to economic development.

The government intends to reach an ambitious goal of boosting manufacturing output's share of the GDP to 25% by FY2025. This internal growth of the Indian continent aims to address existing issues and create fresh opportunities, exploring a grand vision for the nation's economic future. The Make in India program has gained significant traction, supported by skill development initiatives aimed at enhancing the capabilities of the workforce. This support is crucial for providing new employment opportunities for the youth, thus aiding in the reduction of unemployment and underemployment.

Furthermore, the initiative underscores the importance of sustainable growth. While pushing for industrial and manufacturing advancements, the government has also emphasized the need to maintain ecological balance, ensuring that economic growth does not come at the expense of the environment. This holistic approach aligns with global sustainability goals and positions India as a responsible economic power.

To truly scale the contributions of MSMEs, there must be a significant increase in financial and human resources. Enhanced access to affordable credit, investment in human capital, and capacity-building initiatives are essential for aligning MSMEs with global standards. Additionally, regulatory frameworks need to be simplified to reduce the burden on businesses and promote a business-friendly environment.

By implementing these strategic measures, the "Make in India" campaign can unlock the full potential of MSMEs, driving significant economic growth and development. This will not only boost the Indian economy but also position it as a formidable player on the global stage, potentially surpassing nations like China in international marketplaces.

The "Make in India" initiative has already begun to pave the way for a robust and dynamic manufacturing sector. With continued government support and strategic policy implementations, India is well on its way to becoming a global manufacturing powerhouse, contributing substantially to the world economy and achieving unparalleled economic growth.

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